

From: American Journal of Biomedical Science & Research <agri@biomedgrid-nl.net>

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Dear Dr. Schlomi Mattan,

Start each day with great smile.

Well, we are cheerful to inform you that, we have successfully completed Galley Proof and **PDF version** of your article entitled with "**Sedation and Twilight Anesthesia Induced by Ascofregata Purin Song**". Please find the enclosed **attached PDF** of your article and feel free to contact us if any **modifications are required**.

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Await your optimistic response.

Regards,

Catherine Nichols

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